

Linking School Improvement to Teacher Motivation and Job Satisfaction: The Challenge of Change

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ABSTRACT

It is not undeniable that motivation and job satisfaction are important ingredients in elevating individual performance to tap success. It is the same in school setting, teachers who are well motivated are more likely satisfied in their teaching career. This paper attempts to share the motivational practices of some performing countries in terms of bringing education in the next level. Findings suggest that the principal motivators for teachers are promotion, working environment and leadership of the higher authority. It was also found out that increase of workloads affect the job satisfaction of the teachers.

KEYWORDS: Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Productivity, Leadership

How to cite this paper: Roberto Suson | Sheila Pearl Mejica | Ji-an Catibig | Marciano Placencia Jr | Marilyn Miranda "Linking School Improvement to Teacher Motivation and Job Satisfaction: The Challenge of Change"

Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-1, December 2019, pp.547-550, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29616.pdf>

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INTRODUCTION

The past decade has undergone an increase in teacher motivation research across various contexts. Research on school Improvement has indicated that student outcomes depend highly on the quality of instruction, which is interrelated to motivation and job satisfaction of the human resources (Scheerens, 2008). In today's world, in order for an organization to be successful and maintain its existence, both the productivity of its staff and the satisfaction of them in terms of administration, rewarding system, colleagues and job they are performing are all crucial factors. Research on teacher motivation has developed and expanded since the late 1990s, and the past decade has witnessed a marked increase in literature in the area of teacher motivation research across various social cultural contexts. A significant step forward was the release of the special issue on motivation for teaching by Learning and Instruction in 2008 with the focus on relating the current motivational theories to the domain of teaching which has been called a "Zeitgeist of interest" by Watt and Richardson (2008a). As a big contribution to the application of motivational theories in the new research domain of teachers in their career choice, education studies and professional commitment, the special issue was an important impetus to setting the agenda for future teacher motivation research.

Teacher motivation, has been topics of research studies for decades. However, these remain important topics worthy of

examination, as we continue to see shifts in the demands and expectations placed on our nation's teaching force. States and districts across the country are continually facing challenges associated with the hiring and retention of high quality teachers (NEA Today, 2014).

In addition, factors that influence the achievement of teachers are also decisive in the achievement of the work situation, work environment or atmosphere of the organization, namely the extent to which someone likes responsibility based on his work. How good relationship with the association is based on and how much the incentives provided by the efforts made in his work. Teaching motivation encourages the teachers to produce quality learning process. According to Suson (2019) the more an educator is satisfied with his work, the more it will increase productivity or better output. This implies that teacher's productiveness will also depend on their level of motivational factors

Teachers also want to get a strong urge to do their job at school. Teachers who have high motivation in teaching have high achievement. To move forward and have a high achievement in the implementation of the learning process, teachers need encouragement and efforts to develop, improve loyalty and commitment to the profession and receive the award (Davis,2004).

Healthfield (2017) stated that whatever the job is and no matter what your position is, it is very important to an employee that his/her efforts are recognized. If an employee has been spending a lot of time working on a task, or is even just willing to help out the other co-workers, give them applause and show them your gratitude. It can be understood that it is not merely about giving praise. If the efforts of an employee are recognized, he/she will feel achievement and fulfillment and continue to excel in the work. However, it is crucial to consider that the recognition as a motivator may differ among employees as one might increase the work productivity after being recognized while one is the opposite.

Moreover, the constantly changing field of education is very challenging. Teachers need support and guidance to assist them as they learn to be successful educators in the classroom (Billingsly, Israel & Smith 2011). Even after extensive time spent in a college preparatory program for their chosen profession, teachers may feel underprepared for the reality of teaching once they are actually in the classroom and may also experience a feeling of isolation causing them to be reluctant to ask for assistance to avoid appearing inadequate (Ingersoll, 2002). Job satisfaction takes an essential part in the organizational performance because if in schools, the teachers do not have sufficient motivation then there is less performance which directly influences the students the students'

There are many ways to motivate educators in today's working environment. Organizations globally have been using different strategies and approach in order to improve employees' motivation. However, it seems that the best motivator is something that is indeed important in their lives. Furthermore, different people might have different values and approaches and, therefore, being able to understand employees' needs and using appropriate motivating methods can help increase the level of motivation (Gleeson 2016).

Motivation of Teachers to Teach

Demir & Budak (2016) stated that motivation is a triggering power for learning. The lack of motivation means that there is no action and therefore difficulty in reaching the desired goal. Motivation is an important factor in the effectiveness of learning and teaching processes since it is not only a significant factor in students' achievements but also it gives energy and ensures that behavior is voluntary. The significance of teacher motivation research is also self-evident as it is a crucial factor closely related to a number of variables in education such as student motivation, educational reform, teaching practice and teachers' psychological fulfillment and well-being. Therefore, it is helpful for administrators to determine how to attract potential teachers and how to retain them in teaching. (OECD, 2005 OECD. (2005).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a happy or positive emotion derived from the assessment of a person's job or work experience. Satisfaction comes from within a person, in this case is derived from the inner of teacher. A teacher who has a good job satisfaction, has a positive emotion towards his job and who have low job satisfaction has a negative emotion towards work. High or low achievement can be determined by the teacher's satisfaction in work (Luthans,2006).

Sutrisno (2009) stated that job satisfaction is an attitude of employees towards work related to the work situation, cooperation among employees, remuneration in employment, and matters relating to the physical and psychological factors.

Motivation and Job Satisfaction

Motivation and job satisfaction are very fundamental to continuing growth of educational system. It plays an important role in the organization because it increases productivity and goals can be achieved an efficient way and also it takes part in the vital role for educators to achieved the educational goals.

Teachers Satisfaction and School Improvement

Job satisfaction plays a key role in the success of an organization's business, whereby the relationship between job satisfaction and work performance has been shown to be significant, and high employee job satisfaction is important in order for an organization to function and achieve its goal (Usop, Kadtong & Usop, 2013).

In a similar manner, in educational context the job satisfaction experienced by teachers is likewise crucial for schools' successful operation and can bring positive impact to the school improvement. Kwaray, & Ali (2015) stated that those teachers who were not satisfied, due to some factors: lack of motivation, like career advancement opportunities, low salary, or ineffective communication with leader, were more likely to not effective teachers and somewhat leave the teaching profession.

To summarize the above related studies and literature, the researcher believes that teachers' motivation and job satisfaction are incredibly important for the attainment of organizational aims and objectives.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This paper attempts to pose a literature review of the development of teacher motivation and job satisfaction by identifying the factors that lead to teacher's productivity these includes promotion, working environment, leadership and workload. According to Abos et al. happy teachers have better job performance given its association with self-determined motivation and job effectiveness, plays a pivotal role in achieving school success.

DISCUSSION

Promotion

The advancement of a teachers within a company position or job tasks. It maybe a result of an teachers' proactive pursuit of a higher ranking or as a reward by an institution for good performance.

**Figure1
Promotion**

The analysis of teacher motivation and job satisfaction implied on the results that promotion is one of the key factors that teachers become motivated and satisfied in their career. New Zealand teachers were found to be more satisfied than Malaysia, Australia and England. According to Treputtharat & Tayiam (2014) Promotion also helps to boost teachers' morale and motivates them to work properly and more effectively. This increases the productivity and efficiency and enhances job satisfaction. Similar to other related studies salary is not the only external factor to increase the level of motivation, to mean that employees are also likely to be motivated by other additional form of rewarding like getting promotions and other types of incentives (Munyengabe et al, 2016; Alam, 2011). This implies that having a promotion can totally elevate the teachers' productivity towards its career.

Working Environment

The surrounding conditions in which a teacher operates. The work environment can be composed of physical conditions, such as classroom temperature, availability of the resources and safety and security of the teachers.

Figure2.
Working Environment

An additional aspect of teachers motivation towards job satisfaction is the working environment. The results in figure 1 shows that working environment has big influence to ones productivity. According to Munyengabe et al. (2016) A good classroom environment makes teachers and students feeling good and comfortable during their teaching/learning processes. The good classroom environment is not only helpful at the secondary or primary schools levels, it is also an indispensable factor at the university level, and the good environment provides the motivation of lecturers in their everyday teaching activities. The impact of this factor on the job satisfaction was also studied by Bakotić and Fiskovića (2013), they found that workers who work in normal working conditions usually show the high level of being satisfied at their work while those working in not favored conditions were presented with the low level of satisfaction at their work. According to Suson (2019) the product of teaching-learning process is determined not just by the performance of teachers, but also the quality of the environment where they are working. The same as Poggi (2010) and Munyengabe et al. (2016) for their findings they reached to illustrate that working conditions play a vital role in increasing or reducing the level of employees' satisfaction at their work.

Leadership

Leadership refers to someone leading others by motivating

them to strive for certain goals rather than simply act on orders. Motivation in leadership is a goal oriented characteristics that helps attain the educational goals and objectives.

Figure3.
Leadership

Teachers satisfaction is also associated with good interpersonal relationship with the school heads and other subordinates. Based on the results gathered, leadership of the school head has also a big factor for the attainment of teachers success. In the recent study of Munyengabe et al (2017), it was stated that lecturers at university valued highly the respect between the leaders and lecturers as an influential item to construct the good relationship between lecturers and their leaders. From above results, it is seen that if the good relationship is maintained at the workplace the level of job satisfaction will be increased. This implied that good relationship between leaders and teachers will likely attain the goal and objectives of the school. Therefore teachers are happy and interested to work in the place where there is a good relationship with their school head.

Workload

The amount of work performed or capable of being performed. It also refers to a number of task and obligations that you have to perform or complete within a specific amount of time.

Figure4.
Workload

From the findings, the data shows that workload also influence teachers in producing good results. Malaysia has the highest weighted mean followed by New Zealand, Australia whilst England was the last. It shows how satisfied these countries to the given task of the teachers. According to Munyengabe et al (2016) workload and stress level had a negative impact to the overall level of job satisfaction. The findings of this study did not contrast with other existing

studies such that of who indicated that the increment in reducing the workload and stress level impact will go in hand with the increment with the job satisfaction. This implies that workload contributes to the stress and dissatisfaction of the teachers. Therefore, workload of teachers must be in accordance with their stipulated working hours and availability, if given more task, it must received supports from the top management.

CONCLUSION

The information gathered in this study indicates that teachers who are highly motivated and satisfied were likely to achieve their task especially in achieving school goals and objectives. The literature shows that promotion, working environment, and leadership have significantly influence the productivity of the teachers in their teaching career. However, there are also some issues that leads to teachers' dissatisfaction that needs to addressed. It is recommended that future researchers will touch and discuss the issues and concerns relating to teachers dissatisfaction towards their career.

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